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INTERNATIONAL LABOUR MIGRATION FROM BANGLADESH: NATURE, COST AND REMITTANCES

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ABSTRACT

International labour migration from Bangladesh has become an important element of survival for many households in rural areas. Influx of remittances is enhancing the process of development in multi-faceted ways. This study attempts to analyze various aspects of international out-migration from Bangladesh. The study reveals that migrant workers migrated at their earlier stage of life. The role of education is not very much determinative to the short-term migrant workers. A good portion of migrant workers (about 23 percent) had no formal education. A few people (about 3 percent) went abroad through illegal channel. On an average, every migrant worker had to bear BDT 246,802 as direct migration cost. Apart from direct cost they also bore a significant amount of psychic cost. In financing cost for migration, personal saving and followed by borrowing from local money lender contributed the most. In the case of borrowing from money lender, an exorbitantly high interest rate was to be paid. Situation of sending remittances through official channels has improved. Most of the respondents (91.9 percent) sent remittances through official channels. The migrant family spent most of the remittances on consumption, building and repairing of house. However, a significant amount of remittances was spent on health and education by the migrant households. Investment on institutional saving instruments is very low. Running petty business with remittances remained very low as well.

KEYWORDS: *Migrant worker, Migration, Cost, Remittances, Destination, Psychic cost, Hundi.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Labour migration from Bangladesh is a very significant phenomenon. It contributes to the economic development of Bangladesh in multi faceted ways. Outgoing migrant population eases the problem of unemployment and they send remittances to the country, which are the driving factor of development finance. Labour migration from Bangladesh started during the British colonial period. In the early 1940s work opportunities on British merchant ships paved the way for migration to Europe, North America and other parts of the world (Siddiqui et. al, 2008). Since the 1940s migrant population went to different countries across the globe. In the meantime the route and destinations have changed significantly. Present form of short-term international labour migration from Bangladesh started from mid-1970s when a substantial number of Bangladeshi started to migrate to Gulf countries. During that period huge demand for labour was created because of oil boom in Gulf region. From 1976 to 2011, a total of 7,699,951 persons were employed in different countries of the world and they sent remittances amounting to BDT 55,846,273 crore (BMET, 2012). Saudi Arabia is the single largest employer of the Bangladeshi workers. It accounts for 33.7 percent of the total overseas employment. UAE is the second largest employer who accounts for 26.9 percent (BMET, 2012). Wage earners' remittance is the significant source of foreign exchange reserve in Bangladesh. If we take only the value addition to the readymade garments (RMG) sector into consideration, remittances outweigh RMG export earnings. In June, 2012 foreign exchange reserve was USD 10364.4 million whereas remittance inflow was USD 1073.5 million. In this single month wage earners' remittances constitute 10.4 percent of the total international reserve (Bangladesh Bank, 2012).

2. OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of the study are--

1. To identify the nature of migrants and pattern of migration in the selected locations.
2. To analyze the mode of financing the cost of migration, remittance-transferring methods, and utilization of remittances.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study both primary and secondary data have been used. For primary data collection, a survey was conducted in the June, 2012. Four villages were taken purposively for the survey. Ninety households from the four villages, from where at least one person migrated abroad for employment purpose or were planning to migrate, were surveyed. Most of the households in the surveyed locations are similar in characteristics. The surveyed villages were Mhaishmara under Madhupur Upazilla and Shaliabah under Ghatail upazilla of Tangail district; Backchar under Muktagachha upazilla and Radhakanai under Fulbaria upazilla of Mymensingh district. Out of the 90 respondents, 60 were from migrant households, 26 from returned migrants, and 4 from would-be migrants (Table-1). To collect primary data a questionnaire was prepared which was properly pre-tested by the researcher. In-depth interview and group discussions were held with some remittance-receiving household members, remittance recipients, and the returned migrants. Adequate measures were taken during the period of data collection to minimize the number of

possible errors. The collected data were summarized and scrutinized carefully. For secondary data various reports, periodicals, journals etc. were reviewed.

TABLE-1: LOCATIONS OF DATA COLLECTION.

Village	Upazilla	District	No of respondents
Mahishmara	Madhupur	Tangail	20
Shaliabah	Ghatail	Tangail	20
Backchar	Muktagachha	Mymensingh	28
Radhakanai	Fulbaria	Mymensingh	22
Total			90

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

3.1 LIMITATIONS OF DATA

As the locations are selected purposively and population size is not very large, the findings may not represent the actual national scenario. Because of budgetary limitations, survey locations were not extended further. A further extended study may be conducted.

4. NATURE OF MIGRANTS AND PATTERN OF MIGRATION

In the survey area it is noticed that married persons exhibited higher tendency to migrate abroad. Among the 90 migrants 59 were married (65.6%) and rest 31 were unmarried (34.4%). Although a good number of female workers are working abroad, no female migrants were found in the survey households. To get high return migration takes place at the earlier stage of life. Hossain (2001) and Siddiqui (2003) indicated that most labour migrants were young, more specifically between 15 and 30 years of age. The average age of the migrants surveyed was 32.9 years ranging between 19 years (lowest) and 55 years (highest). Average age of the workers staying abroad and the returned migrants were 33.3 years and 31.9 years respectively. Most of the migrants (85.5 percent) went abroad through official channel, only 3.3 percent through illegal channels and in 11.7 percent of the cases, the respondents were unresponsive.

4.1. EDUCATION

Education plays a good role in professional and skilled labour migration. In unskilled labour migration education's role is not very much determinative. In the case of semi-skilled labour migration education in the form of training is very significant. According to micro level studies, most migrant workers have a low educational background or are illiterate (Hossain, 2001; Siddiqui, 2003; cited in De Bruyn et. al, 2005) Most of the migrants surveyed (46.7 percent) had secondary level of education whereas 13.3 percent had only primary education. And a good

portion of migrants (23.3 percent) had no formal education. Higher educated migrants constituted a small part of the respondents (6.7 percent).

TABLE-2: EDUCATION LEVEL OF THE MIGRANTS

Education level	Number	Percentage
No education	21	23.33
Class I to V	12	13.33
Class VI to X	42	46.67
Class XI to XII	09	10
Honours	04	4.44
Masters	02	2.22
Total	90	100

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

4.2. PRE-MIGRATION EMPLOYMENT STATUS

People from Bangladesh are migrating to different countries across the globe to escape from the grip of poverty and unemployment and in search of a better livelihood. Most of the migrants surveyed (51 percent) had been unemployed prior to migration and 49 percent had been virtually employed with meager monthly income. Most of them had been engaged in cultivation with no marginal contribution as disguised unemployment. Others had been engaged in day labour, carpentry, construction worker, garment worker, and petty business in informal sectors.

Pre migration employment

Monthly average pre migration family income is estimated as BDT 5,496. Some migrants' family member reported that they (the migrants) would run a business with the amount needed to migrate but lack of knowledge, experience, chances of loss, and failure hindered them from doing this. From Table-3 it is evident that 22.2 percent of migrants had no income and only 17.8 percent had family income over BDT 8001 with an average of BDT 11,353.

TABLE-3: PRE MIGRATION MONTHLY INCOME

Income range (BDT)	No of Migrant	Average Income (BDT)
No income	20	0
500-2000	10	1517
2001-4000	12	3250
4001-6000	25	5009
6001-8000	07	7571
8001<	16	11353

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

4.3. DESTINATION

Saudi Arabia is the common destination of Bangladeshi workers. This is the single country which received highest number of Bangladeshi workers. UAE is the second largest country employing the workers of the country. Middle Eastern countries and Malaysia employ 88 percent of Bangladeshi workers (IOM, 2009). During survey, key informants noticed that Middle East and Malaysia are chosen as a better destination from religious point of view as majority of the people in these countries and Bangladesh hold the same religion. Other factors of choosing destination country are cost of migration, availability of information, culture in destination country, following the routes taken by friends and family member, following neighbor, and availability of opportunities. Only the wealthy migrants can chose destination country on the basis of higher monthly income abroad. Generally, monthly income in industrialized developed country is much higher than that of other countries. Migration cost is relatively higher in those countries. In the present study majority of the workers (30.2 percent) went to Malaysia followed by 27.9 percent to Saudi Arabia. Next to these countries, 7 percent of workers went to UAE and 9.3 percent to Singapore.

TABLE-4: DESTINATION OF MIGRANTS

Sl. No	Country	No of Migrants	%
1	Libya	04	4.65
2	Saudi Arabia	24	27.91
3	UAE	06	6.98
5	Kuwait	04	4.65
6	Jordan	04	4.65
7	Singapore	08	9.30
8	Oman	05	5.81
9	Malaysia	26	30.23
10	Brunei	03	3.49
11	Egypt	02	2.33
Total		86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

5.1. COST OF MIGRATION

Cost of migration is the significant indicator of both national migration and international out-migration of labour. Returns on out-migration directly depends on the whole cost involved in the process of migration and the time to recoup the cost incurred. Huge amount of psychic cost is also involved in out-migration as the migrant leave behind his/her friends and family. Great attachment to the place of birth is another determinant of psychic cost. Average direct cost of migration of the surveyed workers was BDT 246,802. Cost of migration to Singapore is the highest in present study (BDT 391,111). Average cost of migration to Saudi Arabia, the common destination, is BDT 200,400 whereas it was BDT 262,407 for Malaysia. Actual needed cost of migration is much lower than that the migrants had incurred. Cost increases because of broker based recruiting system in Bangladesh. Although government has fixed the fees, most of the recruiting agency charges over the fixed fees. The broker or middle man or migrant collecting agent of recruiting agency takes extra money by doing fraudulent activities. In case of individual recruiter, visa seller, migrant bears higher cost as well. On the other hand, the surveyed people showed mixed reaction about psychic cost. Although to estimate psychic cost in monetary terms is quite impossible as it is a mental phenomenon, to get an idea of psychic cost an indirect approach is used here. Each of the respondents was asked about the extra amount demanded in

compensation to the family and community attachment to home. 52 persons responded affirmatively and the average monthly psychic cost they attached to the migration process and living abroad alone was BDT 13,411.76.

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

5.2. SOURCES OF FUND FOR COST OF MIGRATION

In the rural area selling and mortgaging land are the common sources of fund of financing the cost of migration. In addition to this, migrants borrow from non institutional lenders, friends and family members. Local money lenders, locally called mahajan, are the main source of non institutional loans. In that case, the lenders charge a high interest on loan. Some NGOs lend money at moderate interest rate. Taking loan from private and public financial institutions is very difficult and complicated. Fewer people are able to collect fund from this source. Personal saving is another important source of fund. In the surveyed households most (35.8 percent) of the fund has been drawn from personal saving followed by local money lender (34.9 percent). Remittance sent by the already migrated family member constitutes large part of personal saving. Local money lender gives loan to outgoing migrant without any hesitation compared to other purposes because of certainty of repayment. In the present study it has been found that the money lender charges as high as 200 % interest rate on loan. Out of total fund 11.2 percent came from relatives and 18.2 percent from selling or mortgage of land. The respondents reported that now people are less interested to sell land as it is being scarce day by day. Out of 90 respondents only one had applied for bank loan but was failed.

TABLE-5: SOURCES OF FUND FOR COST OF MIGRATION

Source	Amount	Percentage of total fund
Selling /mortgage of Land	3,887,000	18.16
Borrowing from relatives	2,389,000	11.17
Loan from money lender	7,469,000	34.91
Own fund	7,650,000	35.76
Total	21,395,000	100

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

6.1. WAGE EARNERS' INCOME AND REMITTANCES

Wage earners remittance is the major sustenance of the health of Bangladesh economy. It is the single largest source of foreign exchange earnings and play pivotal role to alleviate foreign exchange constraint and to support balance of payment of the country. Remittances are used to finance import of raw material and capital goods for industrial development. Moreover, it also increased the supply of savings and investment for capital formation and development (Murshid et. al, 2002). It has far-reaching impacts on the rural development and the standard of living of the rural migrants. The volume of remittance heavily depends on income earned abroad and migrants' residence and citizenship status. The short-term migrants remit full of their income whereas the long-term migrants such as citizen of host country and permanent resident migrant, especially second generation migrant does not remit full of their income to Bangladesh (Siddiqui, 2004). The survey found that on an average, every worker earned BDT 26,314 per month. As most of the Bangladeshi workers engaged in blue-collar jobs their monthly income is very low compared to workers of other countries. Bureau of Manpower, Employment and Training (BMET) has classified temporary migrant population into four categories. These are professional, skilled, semi-skilled, and unskilled. Doctors, engineers, nurses and teachers are considered as professionals. Manufacturing or garments workers are considered as skilled, while tailor, mason etc as semi-skilled workers housemaid, cleaner, labourer are classified as unskilled. (Siddiqui et. al, 2003). In the survey locations most of the migrants (75.6 percent) were classified as unskilled. Remaining 24.4 percent were skilled and semi skilled workers. In the unskilled category they were agricultural labourer, construction labourer, housemaid, cleaner etc. On the other hand, in the skilled category they were motor mechanic, garment worker and electrician. On the basis of monthly income Singapore ranks the highest. Average monthly income in Singapore was BDT 50,555, on the other hand, each worker in Jordan earned on an average BDT 30,000. Average monthly income in Malaysia and Kuwait were BDT 25,777 and BDT 23,333 respectively. The returned migrants informed that income can be pushed up if they were given some specific training.

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

6.2. CHANNEL OF SENDING REMITTANCES

Previously, most of the income of the wage earners was remit to Bangladesh through unofficial channels. Among unofficial channels hundi accounts for the largest share of remittances .In the hundi process the overseas agents collect money from the wage earners abroad and pay the money to the home recipient through local agent. This hundi practice was very popular among the wage earners because of its advantages over the official channels. Siddiqui (2003) showed that hundi accounts for 40 percent of the total remittance inflows. A study of Siddiqui and Abrar (2001) among labour migration to the UAE revealed that 46 percent of the total volume of remittance has been channeled through official methods, around 40 percent through the hundi system, 5 percent friends and relatives, and 8 percent was carried by the migrants themselves. But recently, sending remittance through official channels is being popular among the migrants. Now, sending money requires less time, less paper work and many more remittance transferring agencies are giving quick and reliable services with innovative methods. Awareness created by government and non government agencies also paved the way of sending remittance through official channels. The Bangladesh Household Remittance Survey (2009) conducted by international organization for migration (IOM) has revealed that 81 percent remittance was channeled through official channel and only 18 percent was through informal channel. Most of the migrants (91.9 percent) in the study had channeled their remittances through official channels, only 2.3 percent through hundi, and only 2.3 percent first through hundi then through official channels. Only in 1.16 percent of migrants remittances had been sent through relatives and 2.3 percent of migrants carried remittances personally at the time of coming back to home. Those who channeled remittance through hundi were working abroad in the late 1990s. It is found in this study that none of the workers migrated after 2000 sent remittance through hundi method.

TABLE-6: CHANNEL OF SENDING REMITTANCES

Methods	No of respondents	%
Official channel	79	91.86
Hundi	02	2.33
Hundi and then official channel	02	2.33
Sending by acquaintances	01	1.16
Carrying personally	02	2.33
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2012.

8. UTILIZATION OF REMITTANCES

Proper utilization of hard earned remittance is crucial for individual migrant as well as the economy of Bangladesh. Little amount of remittances is devoted towards investment. However, it is found in this study that a significant amount of remittance is spent for non physical investment like education and health. With the sent income the migrants improved the health and education condition of their family members. On an average, each migrant spent BDT 24,950 and 22,421 per year on health and education respectively. Without remittance it would not be possible to spend this amount on these two human capital determinants. Most of the respondents reported the following sectors where the received remittances had been utilized. The sectors are food consumption, repayment of loan, house repair/building, land purchase and taking land mortgage, buying cattle, assistance to another family member to migrate, education and health. Food consumption accounts for the single largest expenditure group (almost 50 percent). Land purchase/taking mortgage, building or repairing house and loan repayment are other major expenditure items. To attract remittances towards investment, Bangladesh government has already offered some investment instruments. These are (i) U.S dollar Premium Bond, (ii) U.S Dollar Investment bond (iii) Wage earners development bond (iv) Non-Resident Foreign Currency Deposit (NFCB); (v) Non-resident Investor's Taka Account (NITA); (vi) Qouta for IPO in Share market. It is found that these are not popular among the short-term migrant. Information about these investment instruments, exclusively offered for Non Residential Bangladeshi (NRB), among short-term migrant is not widely disseminated. Only one person surveyed reported that he would know about those NRB investment facilities. None had invested in those instruments. It is perceived that these institutional instruments are suitable for long-term migrants. It is found in the study that the short-term migrants are interested to invest in non-institutional instruments such as lending to friends, acquaintances with high interest rate. Other investment areas are purchasing land, and doing agricultural activities such as cultivation, poultry and fisheries. There is a debate among researchers whether all these sectors are productive or non-productive. Mahmood and Osmani (1980), consider use of remittances to

construct or repair of houses, purchase of consumer durables and acquisition of land unproductive while Mahmood(1991),thought the use of remittances to these sectors is productive. Only 14 households reported that they had invested the remittance in saving instruments offered by banks, post office and NGOs; and in small business.

CONCLUSION

This study is an attempt to capture different aspects of voluntary out-migration from Bangladesh. Most of the migrants are unskilled and had primary level of education. Pre departure specific training can enhance the skill of migrant workers and thereby pushing up the volume of remittances. Each migrant bears substantial direct as well as indirect psychic costs. Broker based recruitment system in Bangladesh burdens the migrant workers with extra costs. To finance the cost of migration the migrant depends heavily on borrowing from local money lenders. The rates of interest on loan from money lenders are very high. Wage earners income plays an important role in the lives of the migrants and their family members as well. Much more remittance is being spent on health and education of the migrants' family compared to the non migrant family. The study revealed that the situation of sending remittances to Bangladesh through official channels has been improved. In the utilization of remittances by the migrants, most of remittances are spent on consumption, house building and repairing. The short-term migrants do not invest the remittances on NRB investment instruments offered by the government. Few people spend remittances on cultivation, setting up poultry and fishery project, running small business. The migrant workers face some internal and external problems in migration. Internal problems include delay in sending abroad by recruitment agencies, over charge, hassle in getting passport, lack of institutional loan facilities especially in public sector, brokering, arranging only travel visa, fraudulent activities by broker etc. On the other hand, external problems include being unemployed during some initial months after emigration, underpayment than the contracted wage, attaching to different job, working more than the standard workday, non compliance of the employers, inefficient and inadequate service by Bangladeshi foreign missions etc. Bangladesh government should come forward with appropriate policies dealing with the internal and external problems of the migrant worker. Initiatives should be taken to send more skilled worker abroad so that the volume of remittances is multiplied.

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